

Organic Derivatives of Boron. Part VII. Synthesis of Some Aromatic Borates and their Amine Complexes

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Eight new and five known triaryl borates have been synthesised from ethyl borate by employing azeotropic distillation technique. Pyridine and diethylamine complexes of the triaryl borates have also been prepared.

The preparation of triaryl borates was described for the first time by heating a mixture of boron trichloride and the appropriate phenol in a sealed tube¹. Since then, the synthesis has been carried out with several starting materials, such as boric acid^{2,3}, boric oxide⁴, and boron acetate^{5,6}. The aromatic borates and their halogen derivatives were found to possess insecticidal properties⁷. Recently, Colclough *et al.*⁸ have described the syntheses of a number of triaryl borates by interaction of boron trichloride and the phenol in methylene dichloride at -70° and the procedure has been shown to be the most advantageous.

Triphenyl borate was prepared by Wuyts and Duquesne⁹ from propylⁿ borate also. The azeotropic distillation technique employing ethyl borate has been described in our earlier publications¹⁰ and the same has now been extended for the synthesis of triaryl borates for the first time.

A mixture of ethyl borate (1 *M*) and the phenol (3 *M*) in toluene, on being refluxed and fractionated, yields ethanol, which is removed azeotropically, and the triaryl borate is either recrystallised from benzene or distilled under reduced pressure. The yields are quantitative and functional groups (like nitro, halogeno, etc.) on the aromatic ring do not interfere in the preparation.

Synthesis of ethyl di-*m*-nitrophenyl borate was attempted by either causing ethyl borate to react with *m*-nitrophenol in 1:2 molar ratio or refluxing a mixture of ethyl borate and tri-*m*-nitrophenyl borate in 1:2 molar ratio in benzene. Crystals of tri-*m*-nitrophenyl borate were obtained in both the cases, showing the low probability of the formation of the mixed ester.

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As observed earlier, contrary to the behaviour of alkyl borates, the aromatic borates quickly form addition complexes with amines^{3,8,11} due to the lower electron density on boron atom in those compounds caused by the +M effect from the oxygen to the aromatic nucleus and the -I effect of the nucleus.

Several new stable diethylamine and pyridine complexes (1:1) of the prepared triaryl borates have been obtained by mixing the borate and amine in benzene. 2,6-Di-iodo-4-fluorophenyl borate has been found to form stable 1:1 addition complex with diethylamine, but there is no complex formation with pyridine. 2,4,6-Tribromophenyl borate, however, does not co-ordinate with diethylamine or pyridine. The reduced co-ordinating power of these two borates is easily understandable in view of the shielding effect of six *o*-bromo or iodo substituents round the boron atom.

Neither the di-*ortho*-substitution nor the external co-ordination appears to reduce the easily hydrolysable nature of the aromatic borates considerably, as all the amine complexes as well as the above two borate hydrolyse readily.

No reaction was observed between ethyl borate and acetophenone even on refluxing for several hours.

EXPERIMENTAL

General Procedures.—Analytical procedures and methods for drying the reagents have been described before¹⁰. Phenols were estimated by bromate-bromide method. Pyridine in the addition complexes was determined by steam distillation with alkali and titration of the distillate with H₂SO₄ to bromophenol blue. Melting points were determined in sealed capillary tubes.

Phenols were distilled before use. Amines were dried over sodium. *p*-Fluorophenol was prepared by following the method of English *et al.*¹² and 2,6-di-iodo-4-fluorophenol was prepared by the method of Hodgson and Nixon¹³.

Triphenyl Borate.—Phenol (8.59 g., 3*M*) was added to ethyl borate (4.45 g., 1*M*) in toluene (50 g.). The mixture was refluxed for 4 hours and then slowly fractionated. Ethanol (3.9 g., 3 moles require 4.2g.) was obtained in the azeotrope at 76°. After distilling excess of toluene, the product was redistilled under reduced pressure when triphenyl borate (7.92 g., 90%), m.p. 92°, was obtained at 155°/0.01mm. (Found: B, 3.68; PhO, 96.5. Calc. for C₁₈H₁₅O₃B: B, 3.7; PhO, 96.3%).

Similarly other triaryl borates were prepared. The details are recorded in Table I.

Attempted Preparation of Ethyl Di-*m*-nitrophenyl Borate

(i). A mixture of ethyl borate (3.20 g., 1*M*) and *m*-nitrophenol (6.09 g., 2*M*) in benzene (50 g.) was refluxed for 3 hrs. and then fractionated. Ethanol (1.9 g., 2 moles

* Melting points are uncorrected.

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TABLE I

Triaryl borates.

Ar.	Ethanol in the azeotrope.	Yield.	M.P.	B. P.	%Borate.		%ArO.		%Carbon.		%Hydrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
<i>o</i> -C ₆ H ₄ Br*	72%	70%	68°	208°/0.1mm	1.96	2.05	..	..	40.8	41.0	2.2	2.3
<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ Br*	89	80	74°	228°/0.01	1.98	2.05	97.7	97.9	..	..	..	..
<i>o</i> -C ₆ H ₄ Cl	93	91	..	207°/0.1	2.72	2.74	..	..	54.6	54.9	2.9	3.0
<i>m</i> -C ₆ H ₄ Cl*	90	88	..	198°/0.01	2.71	2.74	..	..	54.7	54.9	2.8	3.0
<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ F*	97	90	..	195-200°/0.2	3.10	3.11	..	..	62.6	62.8	3.4	3.5
2,4-C ₆ H ₃ Cl ₂ *	92	87	85°	211°/0.01	2.11	2.17	97.2	97.8	..	..	..	..
<i>o</i> -C ₆ H ₄ Me	98	95	..	185°/0.05	3.23	3.25	96.1	96.7	..	..	..	..
<i>m</i> -C ₆ H ₄ Me	95	90	..	176°/0.01	3.22	3.25	96.2	96.7	..	..	..	..
<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ Me	96	92	60°	200°/0.1	3.23	3.25	..	..	75.6	75.9	6.2	6.3
<i>m</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ *	94	89	105-110°	..	2.51	2.54	96.9	97.4	..	..	..	..
2,4,6-C ₆ H ₃ Br ₃ **	96	80	83°	..	1.04	1.07	..	..	..	..	..	..
2,6-Di-iodo-4-fluoro phenyl*	98	80	..	175°/0.01	0.06	0.08	..	..	19.0	19.1	0.72	0.54

*New compounds

†Found: Br, 71.3; C₁₆H₆O₃Br₃B requires Br, 71.9%.

require 2.0 g.) was obtained in the azeotrope. After distilling excess of benzene, the reaction flask was kept overnight when crystals of tri-*m*-nitrophenyl borate (5 g.), m. p. 105°, were obtained. (Found: B, 2.52; ArO, 97.0. C₁₈H₁₂O₉N₃B requires B, 2.54; ArO, 97.4%).

(ii) A mixture of ethyl borate (0.304 g., 1 *M*) and tri-*m*-nitrophenyl borate (1.77 g., 2 *M*) in benzene (10 g.) was refluxed for 4 hrs. and then left overnight. Tri-*m*-nitrophenyl borate (1.1 g.), m. p. 102-105°, crystallised from the solution. (Found: B, 2.51; ArO, 97.1%).

Diethylamine Complexes

The new borate-diethylamine (1:1) complexes in Table II were obtained by the addition of the amine (1 *M*) to the solution of the borate (1 *M*) in benzene. The volatile matter was removed at 30°/0.1 mm.

TABLE II

Borate-diethylamine complexes (1:1).

Ar.	M.P.	% Boron.		% Nitrogen.	
		Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
<i>o</i> -C ₆ H ₄ Cl	170°	2.30	2.31	2.92	3.00
<i>m</i> -C ₆ H ₄ Cl	102°	2.20	2.31	2.80	3.00
<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ Br*	..	1.82	1.80	..	..
<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ F	98-100°	2.55	2.59	3.23	3.35
<i>o</i> -C ₆ H ₄ Me*	..	2.08	2.66	..	..
<i>m</i> -C ₆ H ₄ Me	65°	2.67	2.66	3.30	3.45
<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ Me	77°	2.67	2.66	3.31	3.45
2,6-Di- <i>ortho</i> -4-fluorophenyl	118°	0.89	0.92	1.01	1.19

Viscous liquid.

Pyridine Complexes

The new borate-pyridine (1:1) complexes, recorded in Table III, were prepared in the same way as the diethylamine complexes.

TABLE III

Borate-pyridine complexes (1:1).

Ar.	M.P.	% Boron.		% Pyridine.	
		Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
<i>o</i> -C ₆ H ₄ Cl	155°	2.25	2.28	16.6	16.7
<i>m</i> -C ₆ H ₄ Cl*	..	2.10	2.28	16.4	16.7
<i>o</i> -C ₆ H ₄ Br	80-82°	1.74	1.78	12.9	13.0
<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ Br*	..	1.71	1.78	13.0	13.0
<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ F*	..	2.52	2.55	18.4	18.6
<i>m</i> -C ₆ H ₄ Me	98°	2.60	2.62	19.2	19.2
<i>o</i> -C ₆ H ₄ Me*	..	2.58	2.62	19.0	19.2
<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ Me	105°	2.59	2.62	19.0	19.2
2,4-C ₆ H ₃ Cl ₂ *	..	1.92	1.87	13.5	13.7

* Viscous liquids.

Attempted Reaction between Ethyl Borate and Acetophenone

Acetophenone (10.72 g., 3 M) was added to ethyl borate (4.4 g., 1 M) in benzene (50 g.). The mixture was refluxed for 6 hrs. and then distilled. After removing excess benzene, unchanged ethyl borate (3.5 g.) was obtained at 118-20° and acetophenone (9.2 g.) at 65°/0.4 mm.

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